

SWARM INTELLIGENCE SCHEDULING OF SOFT REAL-TIME TASKS IN HETEROGENEOUS MULTIPROCESSOR SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a hybrid swarm intelligence algorithm (named VNABCSA) is presented for the scheduling of non-preemptive soft real-time tasks in heterogeneous multiprocessor platforms. The method is based on a combination of artificial bee colony and simulated annealing algorithms. The multi-objective function of the VNABCSA algorithm is defined to minimize the total tardiness of all tasks, total number of utilized processors, total completion time, total waiting time for all tasks, and total waiting time for all processors. We introduce a hybrid variable neighborhood search strategy to improve the convergence speed of the algorithm. Simulation results demonstrate the efficiency of the proposed methodology as compared with the existing scheduling algorithms.

KEYWORDS

Multiprocessor Systems, Soft Real-time Tasks, Scheduling, Artificial Bee Colony, Simulated Annealing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Real-time tasks can be classified with respect to the timing constraints into two categories: hard real-time tasks and soft real-time tasks [1]. In the case of hard real-time systems, e.g., patient monitoring, the violation of timing constraints is not acceptable. On the other hand, slight violation of timing constraints is not critical for the soft tasks, e.g., telephone switching and image processing applications. Although usefulness of a soft task decreases over time after its deadline expires, it does not cause dangerous damages [2].

Generally, rate monotonic (RM) and earliest deadline first (EDF) are applied for task scheduling in hard real-time uni-processor systems [3]. These methods guarantee the optimality of the achieved solution in the case of hard tasks. However, they have some drawbacks in hard tasks with overloaded situations. The main objective in soft systems is to minimize the total tardiness of tasks. Although rate regulating proportional share (RRPS) [4] and modified proportional share (MPS) [5] have been proposed for the scheduling of soft real-time tasks, they are restricted only for the uni-processor systems and cannot cope with overloads.

Task scheduling in multiprocessor platforms is more difficult than that in uni-processor ones. In multiprocessor systems, the objective is not only to optimize an execution order of tasks, but also to determine a specific processor for each task to be executed. In homogeneous systems, all processors are identical, but the scheduling problem becomes more difficult for the heterogeneous multiprocessor systems. The additional complexity appears from the fact that the execution time

of each task is different upon the different processors. As an example, a mathematical formula calculation may be executed much faster on a floating coprocessor than a digital image processor [6].

Recently, metaheuristic algorithms have widely been applied for the scheduling problem [7-16]. Different genetic algorithms (GAs) have been proposed in [7-9], in which of them, only one objective (e.g., total tardiness, total completion time, etc.) is considered. Moreover, some multi-objective GAs have been introduced [10-13]. These methods were applied for general tasks without time constraints. As a result, they cannot be used for the real-time task scheduling. A hybrid evolutionary algorithm based on GA and simulated annealing (SA) has been utilized for the soft real-time tasks [14], in which, the convergence speed of GA was enhanced by employing the acceptance rule of SA during the population updating phase. The method was followed in [15] with introducing new encoding and decoding schemes in GA. The objective function combines the adaptive weight approach to utilize some information from the current population to adjust the weights of the objective function [15]. Recently, we have proposed a swarm intelligence algorithm based on artificial bee colony (ABC) for the soft real-time task scheduling [16]. The objective was considered to minimize the total tardiness, total number of utilized processors, and the completion time, simultaneously.

In this paper, a hybrid strategy based on ABC and SA (named VNABC SA algorithm) is used for the scheduling of soft real-time tasks in heterogeneous multiprocessor systems. The objective of the proposed scheduling algorithm is to simultaneously minimize total tardiness of all tasks, total number of utilized processors, final completion time, total waiting time for all tasks, and total waiting time for all processors. A hybrid variable neighborhood strategy is investigated to enhance the neighborhood exploration mechanism of ABC and SA, aim at avoid trapping in local minima points and improve the convergence speed of both ABC and SA.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: In Section 2, the scheduling problem for soft real-time tasks and the proposed multi-objective criterion is mathematically formulated. In Section 3, the proposed hybrid VNABC SA scheduling algorithm is described. Simulation results and comparison with the other scheduling algorithms are illustrated in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 provides the conclusion remarks and suggestions for future works.

2. SCHEDULING CRITERION

It is assumed that all tasks have timing constrained. The precedence relations among the tasks can be considered from the task relations graph. The scheduling algorithm simultaneously minimizes the total tardiness, the number of utilized processors, the completion time, the total waiting time of all tasks, and the total waiting time of all utilized processors, under the following conditions:

- System is a heterogeneous multiprocessor system.
- All tasks are non-preemptive.
- Tasks have soft deadlines.
- Tasks have precedence relations among them.
- Each processor can process one task at a time.
- Each task can be processed on one processor.
- Execution time of each task on each processor is known.
- Deadline of each task is known.

Minimize:

$$\text{Objective Function} = w_1 f_1 + w_2 f_2 + w_3 f_3 + w_4 f_4 + w_5 f_5 \quad (1)$$

$$f_1 = \sum_{i=1}^N \max \left\{ 0, \sum_{m=1}^M (t_i^S + c_i^m - d_i) x_i^m \right\} \quad (2)$$

$$f_2 = \sum_{m=1}^M \min \left\{ 1, \sum_{i=1}^N x_i^m \right\} \quad (3)$$

$$f_3 = \max \{ t_i^F \} \quad (4)$$

$$f_4 = \sum_{i=1}^N \max \{ 0, t_i^S - t_i^E \} \quad (5)$$

$$f_5 = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{i=1}^N w_i^m \quad (6)$$

$$w_i^m = \begin{cases} t_i^S x_i^m & \text{if } \tau_i \text{ is the first task on } p_m \\ Z_i^m & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$$Z_i^m = \sum_{j=1}^N \max \left\{ 0, \left(t_i^S x_i^m - \max_j \left(t_j^S + \sum_{m=1}^M c_j^m x_j^m \right) x_j^m \right) \right\}, \quad \tau_j \in \text{pre}(\tau_i) \quad (8)$$

Subject to:

$$x_i^m = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } p_m \text{ is selected for } \tau_i \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^M x_i^m = 1 \quad (10)$$

$$t_i^S \geq t_i^E \quad (11)$$

$$t_i^F = t_i^S + \sum_{m=1}^M c_i^m x_i^m \quad (12)$$

$$t_i^E \geq t_j^E + \sum_{m=1}^M c_j^m x_j^m, \quad \tau_j \in \text{pre}(\tau_i) \quad (13)$$

$$t_i^E = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \text{pre}(\tau_i) \in \{\emptyset\} \\ \max_j \left\{ t_j^E + \sum_{m=1}^M c_j^m x_j^m \right\} & \tau_j \in \text{pre}(\tau_i) \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

$$e_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \tau_j \in \text{pre}(\tau_i) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

In the above equations, the parameters and notations can be defined as follows:

N	total number of tasks
M	total number of processors
i, j	task index, $i, j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$
m	processor index, $m = 1, 2, 3, \dots, M$
s	term index within the objective function, $s = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$
$G=(T, E)$	task graph

$T = \{\tau_i\}$	set of N tasks
$P = \{p_m\}$	set of M processors
$E = \{e_{ij}\}$	matrix of directed edges among tasks
e_{ij}	a binary parameter defining that τ_i or not
x_i^m	a binary parameter defining that task τ_i is assigned on processor p_m or not
c_i^m	computation time of task τ_i on processor p_m
d_i	deadline of task τ_i
t_i^E	earliest possible start time of task τ_i
t_i^S	real start time of task τ_i
t_i^F	finish time of task τ_i
t_i^L	latest possible start time of task τ_i to be executed without tardiness
w_i^m	waiting time of processor p_m due to task τ_i
$pre(\tau_i)$	set of predecessor tasks of task τ_i
$suc(\tau_i)$	set of successor tasks of task τ_i

Equation (1) is the proposed multi-objective function to be minimized. Equation (2) means to minimize the total tardiness of all tasks. Total tardiness in Eq. (2) can be calculated using sum of the tardiness of each task (see Fig. 1). Figure 1a shows the normal execution of task without tardiness, where, $t_i^S + c_i^m - d_i$ is smaller than or equal to 0, and thus there is no tardiness. Figure 1b illustrates the execution of a task with tardiness, where, $t_i^S + c_i^m - d_i$ is larger than 0. Therefore, the tardiness can be simply calculated as $t_i^S + c_i^m - d_i$. Equation (3) means to minimize the number of utilized processors which have at least one task on them. Equation (4) means to minimize the completion time of the last utilized processor. Equation (5) means to minimize the total waiting time for all tasks. Equation (6) means to minimize the total waiting time for all utilized processors. The constraint conditions are shown from (9) to (15). Equation (10) means that each task can be processed on one processor. Equation (11) means that the task can be started after its earliest possible start time. Equation (14) calculates the earliest possible start time for τ_i which can be defined by the maximum finishing time of all its predecessors.

Figure 1. Tardiness in task execution.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

ABC [17] has a good global exploration in the search space [18-20]. On the other hand, SA [21] has very good local search strategy. Recently, hybrid strategies based on evolutionary algorithms and SA have been proposed to gain with the advantages of the both global and local search [14,22-23]. In this paper, a hybrid Variable Neighborhood method based on ABC and SA (named VNABCSA algorithm) is proposed for the scheduling of soft real-time tasks in heterogeneous multiprocessor systems. At first, ABC is utilized for global searching among the search space. Then, SA is performed in order to search in the vicinity of the final solution of ABC. Overall flowchart of VNABCSA scheduling algorithm can be seen in Fig. 2

Figure 2. Overall flowchart of the VNABCSA scheduling algorithm.

3.1. Problem Representation

As mentioned above, in heterogeneous multiprocessor systems, the objective is not only to optimize an execution order of tasks, but also to determine a processor for the each task to be executed. More specifically, the first is an ordering problem, whereas the last is an assignment problem. Recently, SA and ABC have been applied for a popular ordering problem (Traveling Salesman Problem) [24-25], and a popular assignment problem (Multiple Knapsack Problem) [26]. In this paper, a hybrid structure is applied to represent feasible solutions, which is partitioned into two parts. The first defines overall order of tasks to be executed (ordering part), and the last determines the processor numbers to which tasks are assigned (assignment part). The length of each part is equal to the total number of all tasks. Therefore, the number of optimization variables is $2 \times N$, where N is the number of all tasks. It is worth noting that the precedence relationship between tasks with respect to the given task graph should be satisfied within the ordering part. Figure 3 illustrates the representation of a feasible solution for a dataset with 9 tasks and 3 processors.

Figure 3. Representation of a feasible solution for a task graph with 9 tasks and 3 processors.

3.2. ABC Phase

In ABC algorithm, half of colony is the population of employed bees and the other half is related to onlooker bees. At first, the feasible solutions are randomly explored by employed bees. For the each solution, the ordering part is randomly constructed with respect to the precedence relationships. On the other hand, any task τ_i could not be presented before the tasks within $pre(\tau_i)$ set. In order to achieve this issue, at first all tasks that have not any predecessor tasks are ordered randomly and placed at the beginning of the ordering part. Then, the set of all successor tasks of those tasks were ordered randomly after them. This process continues until all tasks would be ordered. Moreover, in order to fill the assignment part, a processor is randomly selected for the each task. The procedure of bee encoding and generation of initial population can be seen in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. An example for initial population generation procedure.

Whenever all bees construct their solutions, they come back into the hive and share the gathered information about the quality of food sources with the other bees waiting in the hive. On the other

hand, the quality of each solution is evaluated according to the corresponding objective function value achieved by Eq. (1). In this way, the quality of k -th bee can be calculated as $nek_k=1/obj_k$, where nek_k and obj_k are the nectar value and the corresponding objective value for the k -th bee, respectively.

In the every iteration of ABC, each bee constructs a new solution, aim at improve its position and its food-source quality. Generally, population updating in ABC is done in three phases: employed phase, onlooker phase, and scout phase. Each employed bee is moved onto her previously visited environment to explore a new solution within the vicinity of the present one. If the nectar (fitness) of the new solution is higher than the previous one, the bee forgets the previous solution and memorizes the new one.

As mentioned above, the employed bee whose food source has been abandoned will become a scout bee. It can be controlled by a parameter called *limit*. Then, the scout bee carries out random searching the whole search space to discover a new solution. It is done like the random search mechanism for construction of the initial population.

The more nectar the food source gathered by an employed bee, the larger probability for the employed bee to be selected via onlookers. The probability of i -th employed bee to be selected is calculated as follows:

$$P_i = \frac{(nec_i)^\alpha}{\sum_{j=1}^{NE} (nec_j)^\alpha} \quad (16)$$

where P_i is the probability of the i -th employed bee to be chosen by onlookers, NE is the population size of employed bees, and α is a constant parameter that adjusts the selection type. The larger α , the more probability of selecting the employed bee with more fitness.

As mentioned above, each onlooker bee selects an employed bee according to Eq. (16). Then, she goes onto the food source area of the selected employed, in order to explore a new food source in the vicinity area of the employed. It is worth noting that he proposed variable neighborhood search mechanism is applied for the neighborhood search in both employed and onlooker phases.

3.3. SA Phase

In general, SA starts with a random initial solution. However, in the proposed hybrid VNABCSA algorithm, the final global best solution found via ABC is used as the initial solution for SA. At the each iteration, a new solution, $Solution^{new}$, is generated in the vicinity area of the current solution, $Solution^{current}$. If $E^{new} \leq E^{current}$, the current solution is replaced with the new one. On the other hand, if $E^{new} > E^{current}$, the new solution may be accepted with the probability of P_w , which is calculated as follows:

$$P_w = exp\left(-\frac{(E^{new} - E^{current})}{T}\right) \quad (17)$$

where $E^{current}$ and E^{new} are the objective function value according to Eq. (1) for $Solution^{current}$ and $Solution^{new}$, respectively. The temperature T is typically considered to be decreased linearly from the initial temperature $T_{initial}$ to the final temperature T_{final} , during execute algorithm. t_{SA} and $iter_{SA}$ are current iteration and the maximum number of iterations of SA, respectively. If $T=0$, $Solution^{new}$ never could be accepted, when $E^{new} > E^{current}$. On the other hand, the larger T , the more probability for accepting worse solutions. Accepting worse solutions allows SA to avoid trapping in local minima points. In order to generate a new solution in the vicinity area of the current one, the common approach as same as in ABC is used.

$$T = T_{initial} + \frac{t_{SA}}{iter_{SA}} \times (T_{final} - T_{initial}) \quad (18)$$

3.4. Variable Neighborhood Search Mechanism

As mentioned above, we introduce a hybrid local and global scheme for the neighborhood search in order to improve the convergence speed of both ABC and SA. Different neighborhood operators are used for the neighborhood exploration. Each operator can avoid trapping a type of local minima points. In this approach, Swap, Exchange, Relocation, and Or-opt operators [27-28] are applied. The Relocation and Or-opt are performed in the first part (ordering part) of the solution. The swap is applied in the second part (assignment part). Also, the Exchange can be used in both parts, called Exchange-1 and Exchange-2, respectively. The five neighborhood search operators can be shown in Fig. 5. Here, 18 neighborhood search structures are proposed from the five mentioned operators, with different segment lengths. In order to explore the neighborhood area of a solution (in both ABC and SA), each neighborhood structure may be applied with the predefined probability.

Figure 5. The five operators in the proposed hybrid variable-neighborhood search mechanism.

4. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

4.1. Simulation Settings

Experiments were implemented in MATLAB R2015a running on a PC with 2.53^{GHZ} processor and 4^{GB} memory on windows 8. Setting the controllable parameters of the VNABCSA is very important and affects on the efficiency of the algorithm. The 18 neighborhood search structures and corresponding probabilities can be summarized in Table 1. Also, setting the controllable parameters of the VNABCSA algorithm can be summarized in Table 2.

Table 1. Neighborhood search structures and probabilities.

Structure #	Operator	Segment Length	Probability
1	Relocation	2	6%
2	Relocation	3	6%
3	Relocation	4	6%
4	Relocation	5	6%
5	Or-opt	1, 2	3%

Structure #	Operator	Segment Length	Probability
6	Or-opt	2, 2	3%
7	Or-opt	2, 3	3%
8	Or-opt	2, 4	3%
9	Or-opt	2, 5	3%
10	Or-opt	3, 3	3%
11	Or-opt	3, 4	3%
12	Or-opt	3, 5	3%
13	Or-opt	4, 4	3%
14	Or-opt	4, 5	3%
15	Or-opt	5, 5	3%
16	Exchange-1	1, 1	10%
17	Exchange-2	1, 1	15%
18	Swap	1	18%

Table 2. Parameter setting for the proposed VNABCSA algorithm.

Parameter	Value
Maximum number of iterations in ABC	N×M
Population of artificial bees	50
Number of employed bees	25
Number of onlooker bees	25
α in Eq. (16)	3
<i>Limit</i>	0.7
Maximum number of iterations in SA	5×N×M
$T_{initial}$ in Eq. (18)	0.5
T_{final} in Eq. (18)	0

4.2. Benchmarks

In order to validate the proposed VNABCSA scheduling algorithm, several numerical benchmarks [14] are performed. Here, a task graph with 10 tasks (Fig. 6) and a task graph with 50 tasks (Fig. 7) are considered for simulations. In the following, we called them Benchmark-1 and Benchmark-2, respectively. The details of Benchmark-1 can be summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Dataset details for Benchmark-1.

i	$suc(\tau_i)$	d_i	C_i^m			
			C_i^1	C_i^2	C_i^3	C_i^4
1	8	19	5	3	11	8
2	6	9	6	5	4	13
3	4,5	18	11	8	6	7
4	6,7,8	37	10	13	5	6
5	6,10	38	10	13	8	11
6	9	37	2	11	11	3
7	---	44	3	10	11	8
8	---	30	4	12	10	5
9	10	37	6	9	7	10
10	---	58	11	12	6	4

Figure 6. Benchmark-1: the task graph with 10 tasks [14].

Figure 7. Benchmark-2: the task graph with 50 tasks [14].

4.3. Simulation Results

In order to evaluate the performance of the proposed VNABCSA scheduling algorithm, we compare it against the four evolutionary-based algorithms named Monnier-GA by Monnier et al. [9], Oh-GA by Oh et al. [10], Yoo-GASA by Yoo et al. [14], and Shokouhifar-ABC by Shokouhifar et al. [16], in terms of the total tardiness, the computation time, the number of utilized processors, and average utilization of the utilized processors. All algorithms were simulated in the same situations in the same datasets.

In order to have an insight into the performance of the mentioned scheduling methodologies, quantitative results are compared in terms of the total tardiness against the number of utilized processors (Tables 4 and 6), and the best results achieved with no tardiness (Tables 5 and 7). Comparison of the obtained results for Benchmark-1 can be seen in Tables 4 and 5. Also, the results for Benchmark-2 are shown in Tables 6 and 7. Tables 4 and 6 depict comparison of the total tardiness with the same number of utilized processors used in different algorithms. Also, comparison of several terms (e.g., the computation time, the number of utilized processors, and average utilization of the utilized processors) without tardiness can be shown in Tables 5 and 7.

Table 4. Comparison of the total tardiness for Benchmark-1.

Algorithm	Total number of utilized processors		
	1	2	3
Monnier-GA [9]	35	19	0
Oh-GA [10]	36	13	0
Yoo-GASA [14]	25	0	0
Shokouhifar-ABC [16]	25	0	0
VNABCSA (Proposed)	25	0	0

Table 5. Comparison of the results with no tardiness for Benchmark-1.

Parameter	Monnier-GA [9]	Oh-GA [10]	Yoo-GASA [14]	Shokouhifar-ABC [16]	VNABCSA (Proposed)
Number of utilized processors	3	3	2	2	2
Computation time	44	42	45	45	45
Utilization of processor P_1	0.59	0.57	0.51	100	0.51
Utilization of processor P_2	0.68	0.59	100	0.51	100
Utilization of processor P_3	0.27	0.47	---	---	---
Average utilization of processors	0.51	0.54	0.75	0.75	0.75

Table 6. Comparison of the total tardiness for Benchmark-2.

Algorithm	Total number of utilized processors					
	10	12	13	15	16	17
Monnier-GA [9]	78	---	---	25	13	0
Oh-GA [10]	59	---	---	19	0	0
Yoo-GASA [14]	22	---	---	0	0	0
Shokouhifar-ABC [16]	17	9	0	0	0	0
VNABCSA (Proposed)	12	0	0	0	0	0

Table 7. Comparison of the results with no tardiness for Benchmark-2.

Parameter	Monnier-GA [9]	Oh-GA [10]	Yoo-GASA [14]	Shokouhifar-ABC [16]	VNABCSA (Proposed)
Number of utilized processors	17	16	15	13	12
Computation time	43	46	47	49	49
Average utilization of processors	0.45	0.47	0.49	0.54	0.56

Results in Tables 4-7 clearly illustrate the positive impact of the proposed VNABCSA scheduling algorithm. As seen, the total tardiness achieved via the VNABCSA algorithm is smaller than those of the other scheduling algorithms. Moreover, the number of utilized processors achieved by our algorithm is fewer than those of the others.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have proposed a new multi-objective algorithm based on artificial bee colony and simulated annealing, named VNABCSA algorithm, for the scheduling of soft real-time tasks in heterogeneous multiprocessor platforms. The objective was considered in such a way that simultaneously minimize the total tardiness, the total number of utilized processors, the final completion time, the total waiting time of tasks, and the total waiting time of processors. The convergence speed of the artificial bee colony and simulated annealing has been improved by introducing a new hybrid variable neighborhood search strategy. From the simulation results, the

results of the proposed VNABCSA algorithm are better than that of the other algorithms. The number of utilized processors achieved by the VNABCSA is fewer than those of the other algorithms. Moreover, the variance of processor utilization rate is more desirable. However, the total computation time achieved by the VNABCSA is a little bit longer than those of the other algorithms. We plan to introduce other local search mechanisms, in order to improve the accuracy and convergence speed of the proposed algorithm.

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